

Tool Artifact for “Imperative Program Synthesis from Assertions by Abstract Static Analysis and SMT Mutations”

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Abstract. In this work, we describe the installation, usage, and evaluation results of the tool, denoted `IMPSYNTH`, introduced by the paper “Imperative Program Synthesis from Assertions by Abstract Static Analysis and SMT Mutations”. We provide step-by-step instructions on how to download, run, and compare the tool’s outputs to outputs described in the paper. The tool is a research prototype tool for synthesizing imperative programs that meet behavioral specifications given in the form of assertions. In particular, we combine basic statement-directed enumerative search, static analysis via abstraction interpretation, and expression-directed enumerative search via (incremental) SMT-based mutations to efficiently explore all candidate complete programs generated from an input program template (with statement and expression holes) until a solution is found.

1 Introduction

This work summarises the evaluation results reported by the paper “Imperative Program Synthesis from Assertions by Abstract Static Analysis and SMT Mutations”. We compare two tools:

- `IMPSYNTH`, implemented in `OCAML`, that uses the numerical abstract domains, e.g. polyhedra, from the `APRON` library [5] for static analysis; the (altered) `CBMC` bounded model checker [1] for translating programs to SMT formulas; and the (altered) `ALLREPAIR` tool [7] for incremental SMT-based mutations. `IMPSYNTH` also calls the `MINICARD` [6] and `Z3` [3] tools for SAT and SMT solving.
- `SIMPL` [8], implemented in `OCAML`, that represents a known program synthesizer performing static analysis in tandem with enumeration-based search.

The evaluation is performed on 64-bit Intel®Core™ i7-1165G7 CPU@2.80GHz, VM Ubuntu 22.04.3 LTS, with 8 GB memory.

2 Downloading

The URL of the tool artifact is available from Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/uploads/13926448>

The files inside this folder are:

- xubuntu.7z.001 (md5:3fae78a22083dae71e6735323f894f32)
- xubuntu.7z.002 (md5:6364aa6d76d39b0a141583a04f36c1ff)
- Synthesis.tar.gz (md5:61b5c3d781df3a6e3b068d0b85fa5168)
- HowToInstall.txt (md5:b9dbb32ecc87670399928aabaf120851)
- Instructions.txt (md5:64c70c5a9ef13673d9286a2ce58cdb93)
- ExperimentalResults.txt (md5:a5f0f9d6480fb1e5bbc8260f675815c1)
- tool.pdf

Once you download all files, use 7Zip to restore VM image “xubuntu.ova”. The virtual machine containing the tool installed and ready to use is “user”: tool, “password”: tool.

3 How To Install

To install the tool by yourself, download the file: Synthesis.tar.gz.

* Untar the given file:

```
tar -xvf Synthesis.tar.gz
```

* Enter the folder that contains the tools

```
cd Synthesis
```

* For step-by-step installation of the tools follow:

```
HowToInstall.txt
```

* Note that you have to install Ocaml, Apron, CBMC, and Z3.

4 Running Experiments

* For step-by-step execution of all test cases of the tools follow:

```
Instructions.txt
```

4.1 Table 1

* Enter the folder that contains the tool

```
cd SPLFaultLoc
```

To run IMPSYNTH on the examples from the paper [4] (see Table 1), we write the following commands.

```
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -noop mult -domain polyhedra bench/hello.c
```

Note: the option “-noop mult” states that we do not use multiplication (*) operator in the synthesis process; the option “-u 6” represents the unwinding bound of the loops; and the option “-domain polyhedra” specifies that the abstract domain used is Polyhedra.

```
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/abs.c
```

```

$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/min.c
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/max.c
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/min3.c
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/max3.c
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/double10.c
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/sum.c
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/sum_m2n.c
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -noop mult -domain polyhedra bench/mult.c
Note that we do not use multiplication (*) operator in the synthesis process.
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/power3.c
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/sum_accum.c

```

4.2 SIMPL

* Enter the folder that contains the tool

```
cd ..
```

```
cd SimplPublic
```

To run SIMPL on the examples from the paper [4] (see Table 1), we write the following commands.

```
$ time ./main.native -input bench/hello
```

```
$ time ./main.native -input bench/abs0
```

Note: (Input-Output Examples are: 1 -> 1; -2 -> 2; -5 -> 5;)

```
$ time ./main.native -input bench/abs
```

Note: (Input-Output Examples are: 1 -> 1; -2 -> 2; -5 -> 5; 4 -> 4;)

```
$ time ./main.native -input bench/min
```

```
$ time ./main.native -input bench/max
```

```
$ time ./main.native -input bench/min3
```

```
$ time ./main.native -input bench/max3
```

```
$ time ./main.native -input bench/double10
```

```
$ time ./main.native -input bench/sum
```

```
$ time ./main.native -input bench/sum_m2n

$ time ./main.native -input bench/mult

$ time ./main.native -input bench/power3

$ time ./main.native -input bench/sum_accum
```

5 Experimental Results

All experiments are executed on a 64-bit Intel®CoreTM i7-1165G7 CPU@2.80GHz, VM Xubuntu 22.04.3 LTS, with 8 GB memory. We use a timeout value of 150 sec. All times are reported as average over five independent executions. We compare our approach IMPSYNTH with the known program synthesizer SIMPL [8] that performs static analysis in tandem with enumeration. For both tools, we report TIME which is the total time to resolve a given problem. For IMPSYNTH, in addition we report SMTTIME which is the time taken by the EXPRMUTATE procedure to check SMT-based mutations, LOC which is the number of locations in the resulting program, ITER given in the form n/m where n is the number of semi-partial programs extracted from the workset W and m is the number of calls to EXPRMUTATE (note that $m < n$ since some semi-partial programs are pruned out by static analysis), and GSMT2 that is the number of lines of the generated `gsmt2` file that includes all possible mutated formulas in the last call to EXPRMUTATE when solution is found. The default values for unwinding bound is 6 and for abstract domain is Polyhedra. For SIMPL, we report ITER which is the number of explored candidate programs. Table 1 shows the summary of the performance results of synthesizing our benchmarks.

In the following, we report the obtained outputs for each benchmark. For step-by-step examination of the outputs of all test cases follow:

```
ExperimentalResults.txt
```

5.1 IMPSynth

```
* Enter the folder that contains the tool
cd Synthesis
cd IMPSynth
```

For each benchmark, we write the following commands:

```
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -noop mult -domain polyhedra bench/hello.c
```

Note: the option “-noop mult ” states that we do not use multiplication (*) operator in the synthesis process.

Table 1. Performance results of IMPSYNTH vs. SIMPL. All times in sec.

Benchmark	IMPSYNTH					SIMPL	
	TIME	SMTTIME	LOC	ITER	GsMT2	TIME	ITER
hello	0.387	0.355	5	1/1	74	0.004	18
abs	1.315	1.160	10	9/3	189	overfit/15.42	288968
min	1.309	1.073	9	7/3	127	timeout	2610000
max	1.110	0.989	9	7/3	127	timeout	2190000
min3	6.059	5.901	13	23/11	221	overfit/0.043	2160
max3	6.369	6.003	13	23/11	221	timeout	2920000
double10	3.041	2.708	10	13/7	205	overfit/0.484	25796
sum.c	1.455	1.383	12	2/1	257	0.005	81
sum_m2n.c	1.286	1.022	13	2/2	294	0.141	4031
mult.c	1.203	0.994	12	2/1	258	0.002	27
power3.c	4.110	3.922	12	2/1	260	0.031	1019
sum_accum.c	102.1	99.2	16	8/3	859	timeout	1860000

Abstract Syntax: : Complete Program

```
[1:]
void main(int n){
[2:] res := n + n;
[22:] skip;
[4:] assert (res == 2 * n);
[5:]
```

```
Iterations : 1
Calls to ExprMutate : 1
SMTTime : 0.355001
real (time) 0m0,387s
```

LOC = 5 (they are program locations [1:], [2:], [22:], [4:], [5:])
 By looking at the temp12.gsmt2 file in the folder "IMPSynth", we can see that there are 74 LOC.

```
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/abs.c
```

Abstract Syntax: : Complete Program

```
[1:]  
void main(int n){  
[2:]  assume (n < 0 || n > 0);  
[3:]  res := 0;  
[14:] if (res < n) then  
[1603:]  res := res + n;  
[17:]  
      else  
[1546:]  res := 0 - n;  
      endif  
[5:]  assert (res > 0 && (res == n || res == -n));  
[6:]  
-----  
Iterations : 9  
Calls to ExprMutate : 3  
SMTTime : 1.160001  
real (time) 0m1,315s
```

LOC = 10

The temp92.gsmt2 file has 189 LOC.

```
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/min.c
```

Abstract Syntax: : Complete Program

```
[1:]  
void main(int n, int m){  
[3:]  res := n;  
[14:] if (m < n) then  
[1603:]  res := m;  
[17:]  
      else  
[1546:]  skip;  
      endif  
[5:]  assert (res ≤ n && res ≤ m && (res == n || res == m));  
[6:]  
-----  
Iterations : 7  
Calls to ExprMutate : 3  
SMTTime : 1.073001  
real (time) 0m1,309s
```

LOC = 9

The temp71.gsmt2 file has 127 LOC.

```
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/max.c
```

Abstract Syntax: : Complete Program

```
[1:]  
void main(int n,int m){  
[3:] res := m;  
[14:] if (res < n) then  
[1603:]   res := n;  
[17:]  
    else  
[1546:]   skip;  
    endif  
[5:] assert (res ≥ n && res ≥ m && (res == n || res == m));  
[6:]  
Iterations : 7  
Calls to ExprMutate : 3  
SMTTime : 1.071001  
real (time) 0m1,110s
```

LOC = 9

The temp71.gsmt2 file has 127 LOC.

\$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/min3.c

Abstract Syntax: : Complete Program

```
[1:]  
void main(int n1,int n2,int n3){  
[2:] res := n2;  
[13:] if (n3 >= n1 && n2 >= n1) then;  
[8894:]   res := n1;  
[16:]  
    else  
[1419:]   if (n2 > n3) then  
[9521:]     res := n3;  
[1422:]  
    else  
[9499:]   skip;  
    endif  
    endif  
[5:] assert (res ≤ n1 && res ≤ n2 && res ≤ n3 && (res == n1 || res == n2 || res == n3));  
[6:]  
Iterations : 23  
Calls to ExprMutate : 11  
SMTTime : 5.900001  
real (time) 0m6,059s
```

LOC = 13

The temp231.gsmt2 file has 221 LOC.

\$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/max3.c

Abstract Syntax: : Complete Program

```
[1:]  
void main(int n1,int n2,int n3){  
[2:] res := n2;  
[13:] if (n3 <= n1 && n2 <= n1) then;  
[8894:]   res := n1;  
[16:]  
      else  
[1419:]   if (n2 <= n3) then  
[9521:]     res := n3;  
[1422:]  
      else  
[9499:]   skip;  
      endif  
      endif  
[5:] assert (res >= n1 && res >= n2 && res >= n3 && (res == n1 || res == n2 || res == n3));  
[6:]
```

```
Iterations : 23  
Calls to ExprMutate : 11  
SMTTime : 6.003001  
real (time) 0m6,369s
```

LOC = 13

The temp231.gsmt2 file has 221 LOC.

\$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/double10.c

Abstract Syntax: : Complete Program

```
[1:]  
void main(int n){  
[2:] res := 0;  
[89:] if (10 <= n) then  
[3211:]   res := res + n;  
[17:]  
      else  
[3189:]   skip;  
      endif  
[25:] res := res + n;  
[4:] assert (res >= 10 && res == 2 * n) || (res < 10 && res == n);  
[5:]
```

```
Iterations : 13  
Calls to ExprMutate : 7  
SMTTime : 2.708001  
real (time) 0m3,041s
```

LOC = 10

The temp132.gsmt2 file has 205 LOC.

\$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/sum.c

Abstract Syntax:

```
[1:]  
void main(int n){  
[2:]  assume ( $n \geq 0$ );  
[3:]  sum := 0;  
[32:] skip;  
[5:]  i := 0;  
[13:] while [6:] ( $i \leq n$ ) do  
[60:]   sum := sum + i;  
[8:]   i := i + 1;  
[12:]  
      od  
[9:]  assert (sum ==  $n * (n + 1) / 2$ );  
[10:]
```

Iterations : 2
Calls to ExprMutate : 1
SMTTime : 1.383001
real (time) 0m1,455s

LOC = 12

The temp22.gsmt2 file has 257 LOC.

```
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/sum_m2n.c
```

Abstract Syntax:

```
[1:]  
void main(int m, int n){  
[2:]  assume ( $m > 1$ );  
[3:]  assume ( $n > m$ );  
[4:]  sum := 0;  
[33:] skip;  
[6:]  i := m;  
[14:] while [7:] ( $i \leq n$ ) do  
[61:]   sum := sum + i;  
[9:]   i := i + 1;  
[13:]  
      od  
[10:] assert (sum == ( $n * (n + 1) - m * (m - 1) / 2$ ));  
[11:]
```

Iterations : 2
Calls to ExprMutate : 2
SMTTime : 1.022001
real (time) 0m1,286s

LOC = 13

The temp22.gsmt2 file has 294 LOC.

```
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -noop mult -domain polyhedra bench/mult.c
```

Note that we do not use multiplication (*) operator in the synthesis process.

Abstract Syntax:

```
[1:]  
void main(int m, int n){  
[2:]  assume ( $m \geq 1 \ \&\& \ n \geq 1$ );  
[3:]  res := 0;  
[32:] skip;  
[5:]  i := 0;  
[13:] while [6:] ( $i < m$ ) do  
[60:]   res :=  $n + res$ ;  
[8:]   i :=  $i + 1$ ;  
[12:]  
      od  
[9:]  assert ( $res == m * n$ );  
[10:]  
-----  
Iterations : 2  
Calls to ExprMutate : 1  
SMTTime : 0.944001  
real (time) 0m1,203s
```

LOC = 12

The temp22.gsmt2 file has 258 LOC.

```
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/power3.c
```

Abstract Syntax:

```
[1:]  
void main(int n){  
[2:]  assume ( $n > 1$ );  
[3:]  res := 1;  
[32:] skip;  
[5:]  i := 1;  
[13:] while [6:] ( $i < 4$ ) do  
[60:]   res :=  $n * res$ ;  
[8:]   i :=  $i + 1$ ;  
[12:]  
      od  
[9:]  assert ( $res == n * n * n$ );  
[10:]  
-----  
Iterations : 2  
Calls to ExprMutate : 1  
SMTTime : 3.922001  
real (time) 0m4,110s
```

LOC = 12

The temp22.gsmt2 file has 260 LOC.

```
$ time ./Main.native -u 6 -domain polyhedra bench/sum_accum.c
```

Abstract Syntax:

```
[1:]  
void main(int n){  
[2:]  assume (n > 1);  
[3:]  res := 0;  
[35:] skip;  
[5:]  i := 1;  
[14:] while [6:] (i ≤ n) do  
[71:]   j := 1;  
[88:]   while [74:] (j ≤ i) do  
[740:]    res := res + j;  
[72:]    j := j + 1;  
[87:]   od  
[8:]   i := i + 1;  
[13:] od  
[9:]  assert (res == n * (n + 1) * (n + 2)/6);  
[10:]
```

```
Iterations : 8  
Calls to ExprMutate : 3  
SMTTime : 99.216001  
real (time) 1m42,115s
```

LOC = 16

The temp82.gsmt2 file has 859 LOC.

5.2 SIMPL

* Enter the folder that contains the tool

```
cd ..
```

```
cd SimplPublic
```

To run SIMPL on the examples from the paper [4] (see Table 1), we write the following commands.

```
$ time ./main.native -input bench/hello
```

```
===== COMPLETE PROGRAM =====
```

```
fun n ->  
  r = n;  
  r = r + r;  
  return r;
```

```
===== REPORT =====
```

```
Iter : 18  
Time : 0.000464seconds  
real (time) 0m0,004s
```

```
$ time ./main.native -input bench/abs0
```

Note: (Input-Output Examples are: 1 -> 1; -2 -> 2; -5 -> 5;)

```

===== COMPLETE PROGRAM =====
fun n ->
r = n + 1;
r = r / n;
r = r - n;
return r;
===== REPORT =====
Iter : 6617
Time : 0.211187seconds
real (time) 0m0,213s
$ time ./main.native -input bench/abs
Note: (Input-Output Examples are: 1 -> 1; -2 -> 2; -5 -> 5; 4 -> 4;)
===== COMPLETE PROGRAM =====
fun n ->
r = n * n;
r = r + r;
r = r - n;
n = n + n;
r = r % n;
return r;
===== REPORT =====
Iter : 288968
Time : 15.41211seconds
real (time) 0m15,425s
$ time ./main.native -input bench/min

Iter : 2610000 To explore : 1188292 Explored : 3798291 Total elapsed : 148.924341
Fail to Synthesize
real 2m33,349s
$ time ./main.native -input bench/max

Iter : 2190000 To explore : 931990 Explored : 3121989 Total elapsed : 149.340226
Fail to Synthesize
real 2m30,310s
$ time ./main.native -input bench/min3

===== COMPLETE PROGRAM =====
fun n m k ->
r = n - m;
k = r - k;
r = n % k;
return r;
===== REPORT =====
Iter : 2160
Time : 0.040116seconds
real (time) 0m0,043s

```

```
$ time ./main.native -input bench/max3

  Iter : 2920000 To explore : 368761 Explored : 3278760 Total elapsed : 149.948257
  Fail to Synthesize
  real 2m31,896s
$ time ./main.native -input bench/double10

===== COMPLETE PROGRAM =====
fun n ->
r = n + n;
n = r + 10;
n = n / r;
r = r / n;
return r;
===== REPORT =====
Iter : 25796
Time : 0.463133seconds
real (time) 0m0,484s
$ time ./main.native -input bench/sum

===== COMPLETE PROGRAM =====
fun n ->
r = 0;
while(n > 0) {
r = n + r;
n = n - 1;
};
return r;
===== REPORT =====
Iter : 81
Time : 0.004669seconds
real (time) 0m0,005s
$ time ./main.native -input bench/sum_m2n

===== COMPLETE PROGRAM =====
fun a b ->
r = 0;
b = b + 1;
while(a < b) {
r = a + r;
a = a + 1;
};
return r;
===== REPORT =====
Iter : 4031
Time : 0.14073seconds
real (time) 0m0,141s
```

```

$ time ./main.native -input bench/mult

===== COMPLETE PROGRAM =====
fun a b ->
r = a * b;
return r;
===== REPORT =====
Iter : 27
Time : 0.001765seconds
real (time) 0m0,002s
$ time ./main.native -input bench/power3

===== COMPLETE PROGRAM =====
fun n ->
t = n * n;
r = n * t;
return r;
===== REPORT =====
Iter : 1019
Time : 0.030958seconds
real (time) 0m0,031s
$ time ./main.native -input bench/sum_accum

Iter : 1860000 To explore : 1156068 Explored : 2976067 Total elapsed : 149.481696
Fail to Synthesize
real 2m31,195s

```

6 Extensibility

The tool is written in OCAML and consists of around 7K LOC. The abstract operations and transfer functions of the numerical abstract domains (e.g. Polyhedra [2]) are provided by the APRON library [5], while the EXPRMUTATE procedure is implemented by modifying the CBMC model checker [1] written in C++ as well as the ALLREPAIR [7] tool written in Python. It also calls the MINICARD SAT solver [6] and the Z3 SMT solver [3]. In particular, we have changed the CBMC tool to implement the translation and mutation procedures from the EXPRMUTATE. The altered CBMC (plus ~1K LOC) takes as input a semi-partial program, and produces as output a `gsmt2` file containing SMT formulas corresponding to all statements in the input program. In case of a statement with expression holes, it generates SMT formulas for all possible mutations of the corresponding expression hole up to size k . The altered ALLREPAIR (~2K LOC) reads a `gsmt2` file, creates formulas for SAT and SMT solving, and handles all calls to them as well as obtained results.

In the folder “frontend”, the lexer and parser are implemented. In the folder “main”, the files “Main.ml” and “Synthesizer.ml” describe the main program

from which the tool performs synthesis of the given template. The tool can be easily extended and new options can be added.

References

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